

TerraDT

Digital Twin of Earth system for Cryosphere,
Land surface and related interactions

UrbanAIR

Weather
Generator

Expanding Destination Earth: **New Digital Twins for Climate, Urban and Weather Applications**

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Destination Earth (DestinE) is Europe's flagship initiative to build an interactive, high-precision digital model of the Earth. Under the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01-03: New Digital Twins for Destination Earth, three projects—[TerraDT](#), [UrbanAIR](#), and [Weather Generator](#)—have been launched in January 2025 to address key gaps in the current DestinE system.

On 10th July 2025, a webinar was co-organised by these projects to showcase how each project focuses on a distinct but complementary aspect of Earth system representation: the cryosphere and land surface (TerraDT), urban heat and air quality (UrbanAIR), and probabilistic weather and climate scenarios (WeatherGenerator). The event included interactions with the audience, presentations and a final panel discussion, all summarised in the following sections.

Audience profile and insights from the interaction

The webinar attracted **131 registrants** from **25 countries**, representing a broad cross-section of stakeholders in climate, urban, and weather applications. The audience composition reflected the interdisciplinary nature of the three digital twin projects, with the largest share (over 60%) coming from **research and academia**. This was followed by representatives from **business and industry** (~25%), **civil society and citizen scientists**, and a smaller but notable share of **policy makers**.

Figure 1 - Audience profile

Participants joined from across Europe and beyond, with **Germany, Netherlands, Italy, Spain, and Finland** among the most represented countries. Other countries included Switzerland, Turkey, Poland, Morocco, the UK, and India, illustrating the global relevance and reach of the topics discussed.

Figure 2 - Origin Country of participants

Several interactive polls were conducted during the event to better understand participant profiles, interests, and needs, as shown below.

Primary use of climate and weather data

A significant majority (47%) reported using climate and weather data for **research and modelling**, followed by **risk assessment and impact forecasting** (20%), and **long-term planning or scenario analysis** (13%). A smaller share indicated applications in **operational decision-making, education/outreach**, or other domains (each 7%).

Figure 3 - Primary use of climate and weather data

Relevance of high-resolution data

When asked about the importance of high-resolution global climate data (5–10 km) for decision-making, participants overwhelmingly rated it as critical. **78% gave the highest score (5/5)**, with an average rating of **4.6**, reinforcing the demand for fine-scale modelling outputs to support local and regional decisions.

Figure 4 - Importance of high-resolution data

Use cases and expectations

In an open-response question, attendees highlighted diverse use cases for climate and weather data, including **biodiversity monitoring, air quality and health risk assessment, natural hazard management, agricultural planning, and extreme event prediction.**

Figure 5 - Use case examples

Highlights of the presentations

Marko Adamovic, Project Policy Officer at DG CONNECT, presented an overview of the Destination Earth (DestinE) initiative. He outlined its goal to develop a highly accurate digital twin of the Earth, supporting simulation, monitoring, and prediction of natural phenomena, and assisting with adaptation and mitigation strategies in response to climate change.

He highlighted DestinE's use of advanced computing infrastructure and AI models to create "what-if" scenarios relevant for policymaking at all levels. The initiative includes a user-accessible platform (the [DestinE Core Service Platform](#)), a federated data lake, and high-resolution digital twins (e.g. extreme weather and climate adaptation twins) offering simulations at finer spatial and temporal resolutions. These enable scenario analyses such as the impact of future heatwaves or storms on sectors like energy or urban planning.

Adamovic described the current phase of the initiative (Phase 2), which focuses on expanding features such as AI/ML integration, uncertainty quantification, and enhanced user engagement. He also presented tools under development, including an AI climate simulator, AI forecasting tools for users with limited infrastructure, and LLM-based user support. He invited participants to explore collaboration opportunities through open procurements and service onboarding mechanisms on the DestinE platform.

Jenni Kontkanen, Project Coordinator of TerraDT at CSC, provided an overview of the TerraDT project and its strategic role in enhancing the DestinE. She highlighted certain limitations in DestinE's current kilometre-scale climate models, especially in representing components such as the cryosphere and land surface. She also noted the challenges in adding new components due to the models' non-modular structure.

TerraDT addresses these gaps by developing new DT components for land ice, sea ice, aerosols, and land surface, as well as impact models targeting areas like forest dynamics, biodiversity, urban environments, coastal infrastructure, and carbon sequestration. The project also aims to create a modular, interoperable software infrastructure to enhance DestinE's climate adaptation DT, improving its ability to support climate adaptation and mitigation.

Launched in January 2025 with a four-year timeline, TerraDT involves 18 partners from 10 countries and is coordinated by CSC – IT Center for Science in Finland. The consortium combines expertise in climate science, high-performance computing (HPC), and impact assessment.

The project has three main objectives:

- 🔗 **Scientific advancements:** Developing DT components and impact models integrated with the core climate models used in DestinE. These will undergo multi-decadal coupled simulations to support more reliable and user-relevant climate projections.
- 🔗 **Technical innovations:** Creating a generic coupling interface and improving performance on EuroHPC systems (LUMI in Finland and MareNostrum5 in Spain), ensuring compatibility with DestinE's infrastructure and enabling interactive impact modelling applications.
- 🔗 **Stakeholder engagement:** Ensuring uptake by the scientific community and public and private sector users through workshops, outreach, user stories, and an adoption toolkit. The project also aligns with strategic European initiatives and international collaborations on Earth system digital twins.

She concluded by emphasising TerraDT's role in advancing both the scientific capabilities and infrastructure of DestinE to provide better tools for climate-related decision-making.

Maarten van Reeuwijk, Professor of urban fluid mechanics at Imperial College London, presented the UrbanAIR project, a new digital twin initiative focused on climate adaptation in urban environments. The project, formally titled Urban Simulation for Air Quality and Heat Resilience Strategies, is coordinated by TU Delft and involves 18 partners, including universities, design consultants, cities, and computer scientists, forming an interdisciplinary consortium.

UrbanAIR is designed to support cities in making science-based decisions on issues such as wind comfort, air quality, green infrastructure, recreational planning, and response to climate extremes. The project engages directly with five European cities: two “action cities” (Barcelona and Antwerp), which are already engaged in digital twin development, and three “learning cities” (Paris, Rotterdam, and Bristol), where the tools will be tested.

The digital twin framework integrates a variety of tools and models: from mesoscale and regional climate models to highly detailed city- and street-scale simulations. These include Large Eddy Simulations, Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes models, operational urban climate and air quality models, as well as behavioural models to assess both short- and long-term human responses. Decision-support tools and uncertainty quantification methods, including emulators and data fusion techniques, complement the modelling framework.

Van Reeuwijk illustrated the project’s methodology through a user journey co-developed with the city of Antwerp, which is particularly interested in heat resilience and green infrastructure. The process involves stakeholder engagement to define priorities, scenario simulations using the Destination Earth “Extremes” digital twin, progressive downscaling to neighbourhood-scale models, integration of behavioural responses, and structured decision analysis with local authorities.

UrbanAIR aims to deliver a functional, user-relevant digital twin that can interface with the Destination Earth platform, enhancing localised climate adaptation capabilities for cities across Europe.

Peter Dueben from ECMWF presented [Weather Generator](#), the third of the sister projects contributing to the Destination Earth initiative. His talk centred on the role of advanced machine learning in supporting weather prediction and climate adaptation through the development of a large-scale, general-purpose machine learning tool.

He began by noting the increasing need for robust prediction tools in light of more frequent extreme weather events caused by climate change. He highlighted how machine learning has already significantly improved weather forecasting accuracy, surpassing the slow, incremental improvements previously seen with traditional physical models.

Weather Generator aims to take this further by developing a foundation model for weather and climate, similar to large language models in AI. Rather than being task-specific, this model will be trained on massive, diverse datasets—from re-analyses and simulations to observations—and designed to handle input and output across scales, timeframes, and locations. It should generate varied outputs, such as scenario-based weather fields, forecasts, or impact-relevant indicators like energy demand.

The tool will:

- ④ Accept a wide range of data inputs (e.g. sea surface temperature, dates, satellite observations).
- ④ Use self-supervised learning by masking parts of datasets and training the model to reconstruct them, thus learning to infer across data types and sources.
- ④ Scale up substantially in complexity, aiming for 100 billion degrees of freedom, far beyond current state-of-the-art weather models (~200 million), approaching the scale of models used in other domains like natural language processing.

Once built, this machine-learning-based digital twin of the Earth system will be tested across 22 application domains, including water management, food security, public health, biosphere analysis, and renewable energy. Dueben acknowledged that it remains to be seen whether such a general-purpose model will outperform specialised models, but emphasised the importance and ambition of this step.

The project involves a strong consortium of partners, including meteorological services (e.g. ECMWF), research institutes (e.g. Max Planck, CMCC), and industry (e.g. Statkraft, Kajo). All developments are open source, with the code already available on GitHub, and the team plans to engage the broader community through mentoring, hackathons, and open calls for application-based services using Weather Generator.

Highlights of the panel discussion

The event concluded with a **panel discussion** moderated by **Jenni Kontkanen** and featuring **Nikolay Koldunov** (Alfred Wegener Institut) representing TerraDT, **Peter Deuben** and **Maarten van Reeuwijk** for Weather Generator and UrbanAIR respectively. The panel discussion was organised in three rounds as summarised below

Convergence and collaboration

The panellists agreed that while each project addresses different aspects (climate system, urban adaptation, machine learning-based modelling), they are highly complementary.

- 🌐 **Nikolay (TerraDT)** highlighted the potential for sharing methodologies, especially in **emulator development** and **coupling interfaces**, which could benefit all three projects. He emphasised the importance of integrating AI-based and physics-based models.
- 🌐 **Peter (Weather Generator)** stressed the value of high-resolution data from TerraDT for training machine learning models and saw UrbanAIR as a promising use case, particularly for linking global-to-local predictions.
- 🌐 **Martin (UrbanAIR)** supported collaboration, noting that AI acceleration is crucial for microscale modelling, and their high-resolution urban data could, over time, be integrated into tools like the Weather Generator.

Adoption bottlenecks and target users

The panellists discussed the barriers that might limit uptake of the digital twins and outlined their user bases:

- 🌐 **UrbanAIR** targets *urban planners*, who face multiple competing concerns (e.g. finance, mobility, infrastructure). Martin stressed the need for *user-friendly interfaces* and avoiding over-automation by keeping the *human in the loop* for decisions.
- 🌐 **Weather Generator** aims to be a *community tool* usable by various sectors (e.g. energy, water, health). Peter noted sustainability as a potential challenge but sees integration with Destination Earth as a natural long-term pathway.
- 🌐 **TerraDT**, closely aligned with the *Climate Digital Twin*, focuses on improving model fidelity. Nikolai noted the risk of overly complex or computationally expensive solutions, which may limit their integration into operational systems or user applications.

Unique value and added features

Each project contributes something currently missing or limited in Destination Earth:

- 🌐 **Weather Generator** brings a *flexible, scalable machine learning tool* capable of handling diverse inputs and generating tailored outputs for many applications without requiring users to train complex models themselves.
- 🌐 **UrbanAIR** offers *microscale modelling* and decision-support tools for cities, particularly in air quality and heat resilience planning. It addresses the need for *localised predictions* and scenario-based planning tied to policy targets (e.g. 2030 air quality directive).
- 🌐 **TerraDT** provides *improved simulation fidelity* by developing more modular, high-resolution models for climate components such as land ice, sea ice, and aerosols. Its modular architecture also enhances interoperability and long-term adaptability.

Conclusions

The panel discussion and the overall event closed with a shared recognition of the complementary roles each project plays within the broader Destination Earth initiative and an overall positive outlook on collaboration and impact. These three digital twin projects contribute distinct but strategically aligned innovations aimed at improving climate and environmental decision-making across scales.

There was consensus that all three projects are developing tools that not only push scientific and technical boundaries but are also oriented towards practical application. The participants acknowledged that while their approaches differ—from high-resolution climate modelling to urban microscale simulation and machine-learning-based generative modelling—they address interlinked challenges and could greatly benefit from shared methodologies, such as coupling interfaces and modular system design.

Confidence in the underlying models was affirmed. The speakers stressed that the models they are developing represent the best tools currently available. The high-resolution climate models developed by TerraDT, for instance, were described as outperforming standard CMIP6 models and offering a richer, more localised dataset. This level of detail provides significant added value for downstream users such as the Weather Generator and UrbanAIR.

At the same time, it was acknowledged that uncertainty remains inherent to all modelling approaches, whether due to physical assumptions, input data quality, or scenario variability. Rather than eliminating this uncertainty, the goal is to better communicate it and offer actionable, user-relevant insights. This is particularly important for Weather Generator, which seeks to serve a broad community by lowering barriers to using complex digital twin outputs through a general-purpose machine learning tool. Similarly, UrbanAIR emphasises supporting human decision-makers—such as urban planners—by making complex model outputs accessible and scenario-based, without removing human judgement from the process.

While challenges remain, particularly in terms of integration, scalability, and user interface design, the alignment between the projects and their shared focus on modularity, relevance, and scientific rigour offers a strong foundation for future joint initiatives within the Destination Earth ecosystem.

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